

STUDY OF MASANUMASIK GARBHA VRIDDHI**Dr. Shweta Kherde***

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20961443>**How to cite this Article:** Dr. Shweta Kherde* (2026). Study Of Masanumasik Garbha Vriddhi. World Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 12(7), 10-12.

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Article Received on 26/05/2026

Article Revised on 16/06/2026

Article Published on 01/07/2026

INTRODUCTION

In Ayurveda, the knowledge of Garbha helps to generate conditions for better management of pregnancy, leading to the creation of a healthy new generation and thus helping overall development of the society. Knowledge of embryology in the present era is the same as that described in Ayurveda many years ago. In the present study, the terms and procedures related to garbha are described properly from garbhdhana to delivery. Shukra and Shonita get united in the uterus, and with the entry of Atma, it is called Garbha. Garbha – Maharshi Charaka says that the Samyoga of Shukra, Shonita, and Jeeva (Atma) inside the Kukshi is named as Garbha.^[2] The definition of Garbha has also been precisely propounded by Sushruta. He states that a combined state of Shukra and Shonita in Garbhashaya, intermixed with the Prakritis and Vikaras and ridden in by the atma, is called Garabha. Later, after the cell division, it progresses towards clear differentiation of body parts. At this stage, it will be called a foetus. The process of formation of the embryo into the mature foetus takes place in a very slow manner & takes almost 9 months.

Garbhadharana: When Shukra and Shonita unite in a pure womb and lie in a pure genital tract, then this results in the formation of garbha. During the coitus after shukrachyuti [ejaculation], vata carries shukra through the yoni and deposits it in garbhashaya. This shukra unites with shudhartava and forms garbha. Panchmahabhuta and Bhava: Different components originating from panchmahabhuta [five elements] take part in the formation and development of the Garbha. Similarly, some components of the garbha [embryo] originate from parents, which are called matrija and pitrija bhava. Atma and satva also have their role in the development of the foetus. Role of panchmahabhuta in the formation of the complexion of the foetus and shadbhava, which are also known as garbhot-padak [supporting the formation of garbha], is elucidated in Ayurveda. Tejas element is the causative factor of complexion, when at the time of conception, if predominantly associated with Aap element, it makes the foetus fair complexioned; that in the Prithvi element causes a black one. If Tejas does not reach the visual organ, it makes the child blind. The same associated with blood makes red-eyed; that associated with pitta and kapha makes yellow-eyed, and white-eyed, respectively. If associated with vata, it causes deformity in the eye. The parts of the foetal body originating from the father,

mother, Rasa, Atma, Satva, Satyama are described as shadbhava. The hard parts, like bone, nail, teeth, originate from Father; the soft parts, like heart, liver, spleen, are of Maternal origin; physical development, strength, complexion originate from Rasa; sensory and motor organs, knowledge, wisdom, life span, pleasure, pain originate from Atma; energy, health, strength, complexion, and intelligence are Satyamaj in origin.

Garbhavkranti

Definition of garbhavkranti, given by different commentators, differs in their way of presentation. According to Chakrapani, garbhavkranti means denoting the descent of garbha. According to Dalhana, the commentator of sushruta samhita defines, it is an upgamanam that means the union of shukra and shonita, in the form of garbha. According to Arundatta, garbhavkranti has been defined as a state of agarbha attaining the state of garbha. Here, the definition clearly differentiates the two distinct states, that is, the state of garbha following the state of agarbha.

MASANUMASIKA GARBHINI PARICHARYA**First month of pregnancy**

According to Acharya Charaka, in the first month of pregnancy, the shape of the fetus resembles Sleshma

(mucoid character) in which all the body parts are present, but they are not conspicuous (Pregnant woman also suffers from fatigue, thirst, etc. in this month. Regimen for the first month of pregnancy - Madhura (sweet), Drava (liquid), and Sheeta (cold) diet consumption. Second month of pregnancy. In the second month, all the mahabhuta (five great elements) necessary in the formation of the embryo get processed by the combined action of sleshma (mucoid character), pitta, and vayu, and become solid.

Regimen during the second month of pregnancy

In this month, Madhur (sweet), Sheeta (cold), and Drava (liquid) diets should be taken. Milk medicated with Madhura (sweet) drugs, the third month of pregnancy.

In the third month,

All the indriyas (sense organs) and minor body parts become apparent, five buds, one for the forehead and four for the upper & lower extremities, develop. Regimen during the third month of pregnancy: Milk with honey & ghrita (ghee), Sasti rice with milk, Krishara (oil prepared with rice and pulse). Fourth month of pregnancy.

During this month, different body parts become more conspicuous & fetus becomes more stable. Due to the stability of the fetus, women feel more heaviness in the body in this month. When body parts are visible, upasneha (attracting moisture) & part of the nourishment is acquired from the passage of the umbilical cord. According to Acharya's Dauhridaya, utpatti is also mentioned in this month, which means the desire of the fetus is expressed by the mother's desire. Hence, Dauhridaya should always be fulfilled; negligence can cause abnormalities or even death.

Regimen during fourth month of pregnancy

Navanita (fresh butter) in the quantity of one aksha (10g) Cooked sasti rice with curd, Pleasant food mixed with milk & butter or mixed with meat soup (jangala mamsa rasa) must be given.

Fifth month of pregnancy

According to Acharya Charaka, accumulation of flesh & blood in fetus is relatively more in this month and due to this, pregnant women become emaciated as rasa is driven to nourish flesh and blood. Mana (consciousness) becomes more enlightened.

Regimen during Fifth month of pregnancy

Fifth month of pregnancy Regime should be offered ghee & milk (8). Acharya Harita advised Payasa in this month (rice cooked with milk & sweetened).

Sixth month of pregnancy

In sixth month of pregnancy fetus derives relatively more accumulation of energy and complexion hence pregnant women suffers, loss of strength and complexion and feel

more tiredness. Enlightenment of buddhi also takes place in this month.

Regimen during 6th month of pregnancy

Ghee or Yavagu (rice gruel) prepared with Gokshura (Tribulus terrestris). Seventh month of pregnancy In the seventh month all the major and minor body parts are fully developed. As fetus attains over all maturity in this month, the women feel exclusively klanta (exhausted). Regimen during seventh month of pregnancy Ghee medicated with Prithakparnyadi Gana is advised.

Eighth month of pregnancy

According to Ayurvedic philosophy oja (essence of dhatus) remains unstable because of immaturity of the fetus in this month. It moves through rasa carrying channels from mother to fetus & fetus to mother. Because of this transfer of ojas, mother & fetus conversely become happy or sluggish. So, this month is not fit for labour according to classics as the life of fetus and mother both are in danger due to unstable oja. According to modern science birth before 36 weeks may be associated with respiratory compromise and failure.

Regimen during eight months of pregnancy

Yavagu (rice gruel) with milk & mixed with ghrita (for anulomana of vayu, the asthapana basti (a type of enema) must be given with decoction of drugs like Badari (Zygiphus jujuba), Bala (Sida cordifolia), Atibala (Abuliton indicum), Satapuspa (Anthem sowa), mixed with curd, mastu (expressed part of curd), oil, salt, Madanphala (Randia spinosa), honey and ghrita, after this Anuvasana basti with oil medicated with milk & the decoction of madhura Gana drugs should be given. Meat soup (Jangal Mansarasa) should be given to pacify vata.

Ninth month of pregnancy

By the end of nine-month baby attains complete maturity and is able to survive in the world on its own. The mother is ready to give birth to the child.

Regimen during 9th month of pregnancy

Anuvasana basti with oil prepare with the drugs of Madhura gana should be given, Yoni pichu (cotton balls soaked with medicated oil is kept in the vagina) (will help in lubrication of the Garbhasthan (uterus and cervix) and Garbhamarga (vaginal canal and perineum). Yavagu (rice gruel) with ghrita and Mansarasa (meat soup) with cooked rice should be given. Daily bath with cold decoction of pounded leaves of drugs capable of suppressing vata should be given.

CONCLUSION

Garbhini Paricharya strives to achieve excellence in fetal formation, its creation without defects, a secure fullterm delivery & preservation of fetal health. The ancient Ayurvedic Literature described in Various Samhita; is not only unique but also scientific with Modern sciences, so Antenatal Care must be done as per Ayurveda.

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